

A web-based service supporting local governments in SECAP implementation activities

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Abstract: *Tackling climate change is of the utmost importance in governments' agendas. The abundance of climate related data becoming available, being published by local authorities and other sources, the digitisation of government systems under the open governance principles, and innovative data-driven services, make available resourceful and previously unseen applications that can greatly support decision-making processes. In this paper, a web-based service, to support local governments in their Sustainable Energy Climate Action Plans (SECAPs) implementation, is presented. The service incorporates open data, published from over 200 local governments, under a unified system. Data driven analytics services to classify them, compare them and recommend optimal policy actions to improve their climate change adaptation and mitigation actions are incorporated in a user-friendly application. The service aims to provide unique and tailor-made insights to local governments, monitor and follow up on their SECAPs implementation, and support their decision making processes as part of activities to tackle climate change effects they are facing.*

Keywords: *SECAP, decision-support systems, data-driven services, ranking methodology, policy actions recommendations*

I. INTRODUCTION

To implement the ambitious climate goals set by authorities at global, national, and local level, in a fair and inclusive way, new pathways, technologies and services must be deployed. In 2015, the United Nations established the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1] to outline the path for research and address societal needs in a way that promotes equity and sustainable development. The advent of digital technologies is a ray of hope on the horizon that can guide and catalyse the change towards achieving all the holistic 17 SDGs [2]. At a local government level, the voluntary-based initiative Covenant of Mayors (CoM) [3] focuses on the active role of local

authorities and increased its targets in 2016, through the Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAPs) in terms of GHG reduction, from 20% to 40% by 2030.

Addressing climate change involves both mitigation (emission reduction) and adaptation (preparing for consequences) actions, which are complex and multifaceted. Mitigation requires changes to electricity systems, transportation, buildings, industry, and land use. Meanwhile, adaptation involves planning for resilience and disaster management based on understanding climate patterns and extreme events. This diversity of challenges presents numerous opportunities to have a meaningful impact on combating climate change.

Digitalization is a key enabler of sustainable development of cities' socio-economic dynamics with the potential to foster climate-friendly urban environments and societies [4]. An emerging trend, is in its early stages of application across various fields, including climate change adaptation. However, a major hurdle lies in the absence of a shared understanding and standardized data, which could significantly enhance awareness and capacity building. Utilizing digitalization to address climate change necessitates overcoming this challenge.

Using big data techniques to extract accurate and sufficient information on urban climate systems is seen as an important way to help these cities become smarter and adapt to climate change [5]. Artificial intelligence and data-driven applications can contribute to climate change adaptation similar to climate-smart technologies. Several approaches in local government level, for policy-related issues have been proposed, utilising data and AI-services. In [6], climate adaptation-related policies from areas such as water management and sustainable development are identified, using the Latent Dirichlet Analysis, using data from public recorded speeches in UNCCC from

2010 to 2016, aiming to understand if adaptation to climate change is important for the countries involved. The Latent Dirichlet Analysis has also been used for text-analysis in the introduction of a methodology measuring key issues in the under-analysis corpus to enhance the debate on political issues, by analysing numerous online files for the period between 1998-2013 [7]. The study aimed to validate the acceptance of anthropogenic causes of climate change, which would constitute the condition for reaching a climate agreement and define a window for political action.

In [8] the ability of deep-narrative analysis in energy policy, regarding the understanding of the effects of Slum-Rehabilitation Housing to tackle energy poverty is analysed. By consulting residents, utilising the text data available and using the Latent Dirichlet Analysis, it was able to extract the most critical points the consultations, with the aim to reduce the bias in the interpretation of energy policy results. In [9], Causal Trees and Causal Forest decision-tree algorithms were deployed to demonstrate that ML approaches can contribute to the understanding of natural resources policies. Analysis and forecasting of the social-ecological impacts of two forest management policies, Cooperative Forest Management (CFM) and joint forest management (JFM) was performed to identify key factors influencing ecological outcomes. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) were deployed [10] for classification of policy texts using governmental data from the United Kingdom, in order to map and analyse climate adaptation actions, and identify high confidence blocks regarding climate change adaptation.

Applications and services aiming to support decision making processes, especially at governance level, are required to rely on open data, in order for the results of the analysis to be accessible and under critique by the appropriate stakeholders.

Data democratisation [11] in policymaking and other sectors will allow access to both the raw data [12] of the services, and to the results of them. Significant results, in the cross-sector between AI-data driven services and open data, are demonstrated in multiple occasions and across sectors, such as the building sector [13, 14, 15], the energy sector [16, 17, 18] and the local governments policy level. Specifically, actions to address climate change are now widespread as decision-makers prepare for its impacts on areas such as transportation, water supply, public health and infrastructure, utilising data-driven approaches [19, 20, 21]. At the same time, the demand for climate data and services that can contribute to further understanding the situation and finding the most effective measures to tackle. Local governments are now publishing and using data (open or private) to support their decision-making processes, with the assessment of their actions producing tangible results from researchers and public organizations, enabling effective and transparent climate change response actions [22, 23, 24, 25].

In the proposed service, a complete web-based application is presented, aiming to provide support in local governments in their Sustainable Energy Climate Action Plans (SECAPs) implementation, using publicly available and self-published

data. The aim of the service is to provide a powerful tool for local governments members, when they design and implement and follow up on their local SECAPs.

Apart from the introductory section, the rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II provides the overview of the service, with its design and main functionalities. Section III presents the results of the proposed service from the point of view of a local government member. In section IV, the conclusions of the paper are summarized and the next steps for further research purposes.

II. SERVICE ARCHITECTURE

The service aims to enhance the decision-making process at city level, regarding policymaking for climate adaptation and mitigation actions. The service offers insights to support in city-level decision making for climate policy through SECAPs, by analysing data from European cities.

The main functionalities of the service include: i) Gathering and incorporating information and data regarding climate change actions related to already implemented activities from local governments and municipalities. ii) Processing and analysing heterogeneous data, to provide unique insights for climate change adoption and mitigation actions to city level stakeholders. iii) Incorporating a unique methodology to rank local governments in respect with their actions towards climate change according to related metrics. iv) Categorising cities with classification algorithms to provide support on tackling climate change in policymaking, by proposing best practices and proof of concept from similar cities.

The design of the web application is based on the standard Model - View - Controller (MVC) framework, customized according to the needs of the provided services. More specifically, the Model defines the structure of the available data, and it is responsible for any updates. The Controller includes the logic of the web application, using the information from the view to notify the model about potential changes. Finally, the View is responsible for the definition of the User Interface (UI). The communication among these server-side components is vital for the functionality of the application. Bilateral communication of these components is optimally managed by the Django-based [26] web-application. It should be noted that the service follows the MVC pattern very closely, but it uses slightly different terminology. Django is essentially an MTV (Model-Template-View) framework, using the term template for view and view for controller.

More specifically, the database that is used for this tool is the Graph database (Graph SQL) [27]. It consists of nodes and edges connecting the nodes. The connection of the nodes is not randomly designed, but it states an actual connection between the data points. Each node and edge can be assigned with properties storing contextual information. The Graph SQL was selected because based on the data that needed to be included in the service (i.e., heterogeneous, numerical, textual, requiring processing) their relationships can be represented through graphs to find meaningful connections in otherwise undiscovered information.

For the service, the neo4j [28] environment is utilised to create the database for the tool. Neo4j uses Cypher Query Language [29] to access and query the data. Through the Cypher language queries can be made through the graph, based on the stored information. Graph databases and their structure provide the opportunity to perform queries, offering semantic capabilities, as if the nodes and edges are named properly it can lead to explainable queries.

The backend environment for the tool utilises the Django Python Framework and its functionality is to access the Graph database and serve the appropriate data for the tool’s functionalities to the front environment. For the front-end environment uses the ReactJS library, in order to provide the visual functionalities to the intended users. The method used in the building of the front-end environment is the “click-to-explore”. This is due to the amount of data and their complexity that can be offered to the user. This method ensures that the user can have a generic overview of all the amount of information provided but can also be able to go deeper in specific sections and information within the tool. The overall service architecture and the technologies used are presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Service Architecture Overview

The input data use for this service, provided from the Unified Reporting System Questionnaires of ICLEI-CDP [citation], are comprising questions from several categories (as presented in the Unified Reporting System Questionnaires). These categories are summarised as follows. i) City General Information, including general information regarding the city, such as boundaries, population and administrative details. ii) Governance and Data Management, including information regarding data governance activities and data management that local governments are implementing. iii) Climate Hazards, including information regarding the identified climate hazards that a city is facing, such as the severity, frequency, affection of economic areas and vulnerable social groups (elders, children and women, children, people with disability, etc.), projections of future severity, etc. iv) Mitigation and

Adaptation Actions, including information regarding the actions which cities are implementing or plan to implement to tackle the identified climate hazards. iv) City Emissions, including information regarding the emissions that the city is producing, goals and actions to reduce them, targets achieved, future projections, etc. v) Energy, including information regarding the city’s electricity mix, the RES penetration, the future projections, etc. iv) Buildings, including information regarding the CO2 emissions, targets to reduce them, energy target for efficient buildings, etc. vii) Transport, including information regarding the public transportation use in the city’s boundaries, the percentage of use in different vehicles, etc.

Utilising the available data, the service offers two types of analytics functionalities to support local governments. The first one is the ranking methodology implemented, to assess and compare cities through a common framework regarding their actions to tackle the climate change. Seven different categories have been identified, each one providing a single score for each category, before aggregating all of them into a single metric. This process aims to calculate the actions of each city and provide insights on how each city is performing in comparison to previous years and other cities in the same year. The selection of metrics to create the methodology is based on the ICLEI questionnaires’ structure. The questionnaires evolve over the years, as new information is being requested or questions are being retracted. This leads to the need to process the information within and combine questions for the methodology to be comparable each year as much as possible. Furthermore, it has been noticed that a lot of questions are not being answered (providing answers is not mandatory by the local governments), and this affects the representation that each city will have in the methodology.

The selection of the questions that would be used as indicators and would make up the metrics based on both the categorization given by ICLEI questionnaires and considered critical, i.e., the possibility of elimination from future questionnaires is minimal. These are questions that provide essential information regarding the present situation in which a local government is, and the awareness it shows on climate issues through its activities and the attempt to take appropriate measures to deal with them. The metrics considered, along with a description of the information contained by the questions, are the following (based on 2021 questionnaires, as 2022 results are not available at the time of writing).

- Governance metric, using indices that measure a city’s activities and abilities to address climate change through internal infrastructure and resource allocation. It considers factors such as strategic decisions for sustainability, joint initiatives, opportunities for local governments to combat climate change, and the support and cooperation of local companies.
- Climate change adaptation metric, using indices that measure cities’ activities and abilities to address climate hazards they are or will be facing. This metric takes into account the identification of these hazards, corresponding adaptation actions, risk assessment for health issues, and factors that challenge or support the ability to adapt.

- Renewable energy metric, using indices that assess cities' activities and abilities to promote clean energy within their boundaries. This metric considers relevant actions taken to support the increase of renewable energy capacity, as well as the percentage of clean energy use within their electricity mix in current or future target years.
- Transportation metric, using indices that measure cities' activities and ability to promote the use of public transportation and low-emission transportation systems. This metric considers factors such as the amount of transit used each year for different means of transportation, availability of charging spots, and air quality information.
- GHG emissions metric, using indices which evaluate city response to effective greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions measuring, monitoring, reporting and verification processes. It evaluates the emissions inventory quality, under defined methodologies and covering representative sources of emissions. In addition, it assesses the relevance and impact of cities GHG emissions reduction targets in alignment to the Paris Agreement.
- Waste management metric, using indices that assess cities' activities and abilities to ensure safe and secure waste disposal. This metric considers factors such as per capita waste disposal, regulations, initiatives and legislation followed for safe disposal, the type of disposal activities, and the amount of recycling material.
- Water security metric, using indices that measure cities' activities and abilities to assess the access and security of clean water for their inhabitants. This metric considers factors such as clean water access and strategic plans for water management, factors and hazards affecting water security in the future, and corresponding adaptation actions.

Classification of cities is the second analytic service implemented. Taking on the results of the cities' ranking methodology and their answers in the questions, it provides 5 different clusters using the k-means algorithm. The aim of the service is to identify, through similarities matching, cities that perform similar and provide recommendations on how to improve their score in the ranking categories. The classification of the cities and their score in the ranking methodology are utilised to provide cities recommendations regarding the potential actions they could take in order to achieve a higher score in the ranking methodology, derived from similar actions that other cities have taken.

Finally, the service has been designed to support easy integration of external data sources due to the use of the graph database and the neo4j framework and the ranking methodology, as it is updated annually, and the questions are being updated on the Unified Reporting System Questionnaires. This ability can demonstrate the potential of the service, when local governments are publishing further data, and provide additional analysis in the analytics functionalities provided by the service.

III. USE CASE IN SUPPORTING LOCAL GOVERNMENT SECAP ACTIONS

The service provides several dashboards and data visualisation techniques, incorporating both the functionalities mentioned above, as well as the available data. In that way, the user of the service can view the qualitative data, i.e., the answers each city has reported in order to view climate hazards and mitigation/adaption actions adopted by other local governments, as well as the designated analysis through the ranking methodology and the recommendations of improving their score.

In the home page (Figure 2) of the service all the cities of the current year in which data are collected are displayed. Each city is clickable, in which the user can enter into more detail regarding the stored information. For each of the categories that are included in the ranking methodology further information can be displayed by clicking on the drop-down menu and analysis on how the methodology calculate the scores.

Fig. 2: Service Main Page

Information regarding the hazards each city is facing along with the social impact, population cluster and assets affecting and the relative adaptation actions along with the ongoing status and their finance status can be displayed through a filtering function, as presented in Figure 3. The service displays the most recent information, which at the time of writing concerns the 2021 questionnaires.

Fig. 3: Climate Hazards Filtering Functionality

For each local government, its main page displays the city's results in the city ranking methodology, as displayed in the figure 5. The user can select to display each year's city score and by hovering on each of the metrics, an information box with details regarding the categories and the metrics are displayed. The recommendations to improve their score are also included, deriving from the k-means similarity matching between similar cities. This functionality aims to support local governments in the identification of critical issues regarding their actions in climate change and help them to focus their efforts in the recommended areas.

A dedicated table section is displayed (Figure 6), in order for cities to be able to compare their performance in the ranking methodology, between their scores, the average city score and the most similar cities' scores (through the clustering algorithm). This functionality aims to assess how the city is performing with other cities and proceed with exploring the implementation actions of other local governments in order to identify good practices and potential actions that other local governments have implemented.

As every local government provides answers to the Unified Reporting System Questionnaires, the user can view the score of the ranking methodology throughout the years (Figure 7). This functionality aims to support the local government members in monitoring their progress and observing tangible results of their implementation actions.

A final functionality is the ability to generate a PDF report (Figures 3-4) with a single click for each local government, summarising key information in one place. As the service contains much information within, it is practical to provide the insights and the most useful information in an easy manner, to support local governments in their policy decision-making.

The report provides an overview to the local government city member, regarding the score of their city in comparison to all the cities, but also similar cities (utilising the classification analytic service), as presented in the pictures below. Finally, in the report, the recommendations for the actions that the local government could implement in order to increase its score is also provided, as seen in the following figure (a random city is selected, as this information is available only for the local government members).

Recommendations

- Please report on your efforts in identification of the climate change adaptation and resilience plan implementation efforts
- Please report on efforts regarding the creation of a climate change adaptation and resilience plan
- Please report on retrofit programs in the buildings of the city

Fig. 3: City's PDF Report (1/2)

CITY OF PARIS REPORT 2021

City's Ranking

Report Overview

Commitment 2020	True
Action plan expected	True
Date of adhesion	16/12/2008
Commitment 2030	True
Covenant phase	action_plan
Commitment mayoradapt	False

Overall Rankings

Metric	City Rankings	Average Rankings (Total)
Emissions metric	0.6	0.3
Local government metric	0.8	0.3
Water security metric	0.7	0.5
Renewable energy metric	0.2	0.1
Adaptation metric	0.7	0.2
Transport metric	0.2	0.2
Waste metric	0.4	0.3
Total average	0.5	0.3

Fig. 4: City's PDF Report (2/2)

City's Ranking

Scale: 0.1 to 1.0

Metric Scores (approximate):

- Emissions metric: 0.6
- Local government metric: 0.8
- Water security metric: 0.7
- Renewable energy metric: 0.2
- Adaptation metric: 0.7
- Transport metric: 0.2
- Waste metric: 0.4
- Total average: 0.5

[VIEW PDF REPORT](#)

How to improve your score

- Please report on your efforts in identification of the climate change adaptation and resilience plan implementation efforts
- Please report on efforts regarding the creation of a climate change adaptation and resilience plan
- Please report on retrofit programs in the buildings of the city

Fig. 5: City's Ranking Methodology Scoring and Recommendation Actions

Check how your city's metric scores compared to others

Metric	Your city score	All cities average score	Similar cities average score	
Emissions Metric	0.31	0.27	0.32	Performing better than 73.17% of cities in Emissions Metric
Renewable Energy Metric	0.19	0.12	0.09	Performing better than 76.83% of cities in Renewable Energy Metric
Adaptation Metric	0.2	0.27	0.34	Performing better than 37.2% of cities in Adaptation Metric
Water Security Metric	0.59	0.48	0.54	Performing better than 76.22% of cities in Water Security Metric
Waste Metric	0.43	0.3	0.47	Performing better than 87.8% of cities in Waste Metric
Transport Metric	0.17	0.17	0.16	Performing better than 88.41% of cities in Transport Metric
Local Government Metric	0.2	0.26	0.34	Performing better than 45.12% of cities in Local Government Metric
Total Metric	0.30	0.27	0.32	Your city is performing better than 71.95% of cities

Fig. 6: City's Ranking Methodology Scoring and Comparison with other cities

Your city's score through years

Municipality of Madrid_2021	2020	2021
Emissions Metric	0.36	0.31
Renewable Energy Metric	0.08	0.19
Adaptation Metric	0.08	0.2
Water Security Metric	0.54	0.59
Waste Metric	0.55	0.43
Transport Metric	0.15	0.17
Local Government Metric	0.04	0.2

Fig. 7: City's Ranking Methodology Scoring throughout the years

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an integrated service to support local governments in their SECAPs implementation action is presented. The service aims to provide meaningful insights, utilising self-reported common structured data, for both visualisations and enhanced data-driven analysis. For this purpose, a web-based application has been developed and demonstrated in the point of view of a local government member user. The overall architecture of the service demonstrates the ability to handle, process and present complex qualitative and quantitative data, in a way that will add value to city-level policymakers, along with data-driven analytics services.

Users of the service are able to track and monitor their local government actions and view how they score in the unique Ranking Methodology functionality. This will enable to

provide valuable insights regarding on how they can improve their actions and compare what other local governments are implementing.

Future actions involve the continuous monitoring of the Unified Reporting System Questionnaires, in order to enhance and adapt the methodology and consequently the recommendation actions with new and up to date information. The ability to gain actionable results from the questionnaires, is also envisioned to be an extra tool, on the cities' internal processes and enable them to share more data and answer the questions in a higher percentage. Doing so, the methodology will become more robust and will reflect their current status more accurately, thus allowing the service to provide even more formidable results.

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